

1 **Activation of Linc01521 by HPV16 E7.**

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6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Linc01521* by
9 HPV16 HPV E7.

10 Citations

11 1. McLaughlin-Drubin, M.E. and Münger, K., 2009. The human papillomavirus E7 oncoprotein.
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